

Design of Innovative Product by Handcrafting of Waste Silk Cocoons

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Abstract:

Silk is known as the "Queen" of textile fibers, and has been used since ancient times due to its unique properties such as draping, shimmering, and vivid painting. Since it is derived from silk cocoons produced by silkworms grown using safe environmental practices, which generally exclude the use of pesticides and only use minute amounts of compost fertilizers, it is regarded as a natural ecological fiber. This aspect is further supported by the chemical and physical characteristics of the material, such as its neutral pH scale, flexibility, lack of electrical conductivity, and high absorption capacity that makes it comfortable to wear. Individuals utilize silk made by the domesticated silkworm, *Bombyx mori*. The lepidopterous insect that produces silkworms is a member of the Lepidoptera order of insects, which also includes moths and butterflies. Good and healthy cocoons are used for extraction of silk but defective and pierced cocoons cannot be reeled to produce raw silk. Those waste cocoons were dyed and **handcrafted to produce cocoon flowers, cocoon flower bouquets, cocoon flower garlands, and cocoon home decorative products.**

Keywords: Cocoon, Decorative, Ecological, Lepidoptera, Silkworms

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1. Introduction

Individuals use silk from the tamed silkworm, *Bombyx mori*. The silkworm is a caterpillar of a lepidopterous insect in the order Lepidoptera, which includes moths and butterflies. Lepidoptera are holometabolous bugs, which means they undergo complete transformation over the course of their life. Silkworm moths, like butterflies, begin their lives as an egg that hatches into a developing, caring caterpillar. When a silkworm has consumed enough, it constructs a cocoon out of silk filaments. Within that cover, it changes into a pupa. After several days, a fully grown silkworm moth emerges from a spit-absorbed gap at the lower part of the cocoon. Dissecting a silkworm cocoon before the adult emerges reveals varied insights regarding the development of a silkworm into an adult moth, which is usually difficult to inspect through the walls of a cocoon once it has matured. During this, scientists dissect a cocoon and 'degum' it to reveal the macromolecule protein known as fibroin, which scientists use to build new materials. A silkworm builds its cocoon from the outside in, beginning with a platform on which it can rest while weaving, eventually tying the cocoon to surrounding plants. As the silkworm works its way into the cocoon's center point, the silk utilized to construct it thickens but becomes progressively narrow. The silkworm caterpillar is completely sheathed within after building its cocoon. There, it will gradually stop moving and shed its skin-like caterpillar exoskeleton to emerge as a pupa, the intermediate stage between the caterpillar and the adult moth. The exoskeleton, known as exuviae is left in the cocoon's lower part [1].

Silk is "the Queen" of textile fibers, being utilized from the old days owing to its special characteristics, draping, shining and bright painting. It's viewed as a natural ecological fiber since it's made of silk cocoons achieved in silkworm growing using harmless environmentally friendly technologies, which incorporates tiny quantities of compost fertilizers and primarily no pesticides [2]. This side is likewise supported by its chemical and physical qualities such as: neutral pH scale, elasticity, lack of electricity, high absorption capability that makes it comfy to wear.

Silk materials and clothes have an expensive look, lovely touch, novel shining and high security for human body movements to be needed and worn both by men and ladies [2]. Natural silk conjointly utilized in gadgets, physics and for clinical functions. Their fineness and obstruction create traditional silk fibers to be effectively used for manufacturing an enormous assortment of fabrics and extravagant clothes, however additionally bands and embroideries and different valuable things [2]. Therefore, silk worm rearing has been still an important financial branch, being practiced in around 40 nations.

Silk is a novel fiber. It has a characteristic reflexive look and has had an elegant history spreading over thousands of years. As of late, "bio-based polymers" have drawn in important thought since they will be used to foster carbon unbiased materials and bearable materials [3, 4, 5]. Since silk may be a bio-based compound, the silk business is going to be a good model for the recent chemo-organic cycle. Right now, the Japanese silk business is in decay [5] and is compromised by elimination. At that time, the inquiry that emerges is that the means of silk culture may be safeguarded. To ensure the safeguarding of the silk culture, two things ought to be urgently done: eco-accommodating silk merchandise with additional value and a skillful silk creation framework need to be created. Cocoon may be a quite exceptional and important biopolymer composite in nature with extraordinary microstructure and environmental capacities. It's been incontestable that cocoon, aside from its undeniable textile application, present uses of great interests in the field of biomedicine and tissue designing. The spectacular art of crafting silk waste is one amongst the fascinating utilities of silk that develop human skills besides generating self-employment and extra revenue.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Required materials for cocoon crafting

The primary raw material (cut/pierced cocoons) was obtained from Central Silk Technological Research Institute, Central Silk Board, Bangalore. These cocoons were ripped open from one end, and the cap piece, as well as the cocoon body, were used to manufacture several handcraft products. Depending on the type of cocoon handicraft to be designed, the following equipment are required: scissors, zig-zag scissors, blade, cotton thread, cardboard, drawing sheets, needles, fabric glue, craft paper, glaze paper, velvet paper, adhesive tape, colour tape, stapler, plastic ornamental material, soft binding wire, beads, chemical dyes, and dyeing vessel, as well as a heater for cocoon dyeing, are all required. Instead of using heaters, firewood used for domestic purposes that are used to dye cocoons. Fabric paint and water colour was used to make cocoon crafts.

2.2 Extraction of silk

The Silkworm Life Cycle begins when the female silk moth lays eggs. The larvae or caterpillar enters the picture as soon as the eggs hatch. After eating mulberry leaves, the silkworms pupate. The silkworm spins a net around itself to keep itself together during the pupa stage. Many caterpillars form a protective layer around the pupa, which is known as a cocoon. The silk moth's cocoon, which is used to make the yarn. Silk processing refers to the extraction of silk from the cocoon. By exposing the silk to sunlight, it is separated from the cocoon. When silk is extracted, it is reeled, which is the process of unwinding silk from the cocoon. Following the reeling process, the silk thread is bleached before being spun into silk thread. The silk production process is depicted in the flowchart below figure 1. China, India, Thailand, Korea, Brazil, France, Italy, and Japan are the top silk producers. In China, the silk industry employs approximately one million people. The Silk sector employs approximately 7.9 billion people in India. China is the world's largest producer of silk, with India coming in second with up to 2000 metric tonnes produced per year [6, 7].

Figure 1: Extraction flow process

Silk cocoons are made from a naturally occurring polymer protein material. A silk cocoon's primary component is fibroin, and the outside is covered by four layers of sericin with varying molecular weights. Sericin makes up 25 to 30% of silk cocoons. Degumming is usually required in the textile industry to obtain silk from cocoons. The removal of sericin improves the sheen, softness, smoothness, whiteness, and dyeability of silk cocoon fibres. As a result, the extracted sericin solution is frequently an unused by-product of the textile industry. Every year, approximately 50,000 tonnes of sericin are discarded globally, putting a strain on the environment. Sericin contains 18 amino acids, the most important of which are serine, histidine, glycine, threonine, tyrosine, and aspartic acid, and glutamic acid. Furthermore, sericin is a promising biological material due to its antioxidant capacity, moisturising capacity, corrosion resistance, antibacterial activity, and UV radiation protection [8].

2.3 Fiber properties

A couple of fibroin brins with a sericin coating are silk fibres that are transformed into cocoons. It serves as the nonwoven composite network stage for the cocooning and links the fibres together in a damp or clammy covering. To examine if intrinsic fibre brin characteristics may have a demonstrably significant role in cocoon qualities, reference non-degummed fibres with perfect sericin coatings were disentangled from cocoons. The average of the helpless relationship between the parameters of the fibre and the cocoon, as shown in Fig. 2. Fig 2 shows that the fiber strength has little relationship with cocoon strength, which is the average of the connection among fiber and cocoon properties. All the fibers share a comparable starting modulus and a yield at 2 – 4% strain. Significantly, most fibers have a resist break around 16%. Starting examination of the information may give the impression of high fluctuation between silk types, yet a similar plot for a solitary silk type, a *S. pyri* fiber, shows practically identical example variability. Various layers in cocoons contrast significantly, and surprisingly spatially close examples can be altogether different because of elements, for example, twisting of the fibers in the movement the worm makes while turning the cocoon. Different perceptions on *B. mori* report diverse malleable properties in various layers of the cocoons. As a result of factors like the twisting of the strands caused by the worm rotating the cocoon, for example, various layers in cocoons contrast greatly, and unexpectedly near specimens might be completely different.

Figure 2: Fibre properties of cocoon

It has been successfully demonstrated that the degumming interaction can influence the mechanical conduct of fibres degummed with various specialists and so ease us from the spirit strating the mechanical conduct of fibres. The construction and characteristics of the fibres themselves can be severely harmed by the harsh degumming technique required for extremely strong coons. Most fundamentally, non-degummed fibres would have larger cross-sectional areas than degummed due to the more fragile sericin layer, resulting in poorer strength and modulus values when compared.

2.4 Dyeing of cocoons

Typically, silk is dyed at the fabric or yarn stage. Various investigations into the colour characteristics of silk fabric and yarn have been conducted. As far as anyone is concerned, no creative and rational research on silk dyeing has been done during the silkworm cocoon stage. The objects aesthetic appeal is increased by the many hues that provide attraction and appeal to them. A crucial component of cocoon handicraft planning is dyeing or colouring, which gives the cocoons a shaded appearance. It should ideally be tinted with natural pigments to highlight the craftsman's originality and give value to it. The silk yarn or cloth can also be coloured using artificial colours. Only soft water can be used to colour the cocoons because hard water consumes more colour and may cause uneven dyeing. The water is made to bubble, and the appropriate amount of colour powder is added. Approximately, 1 kg cocoon requires about 100 gm of colour. First, combine it with 100 ml of hot water. It is constantly mixed to avoid the formation of clumps and to filter the colour solution. The dye solution is then added to the boiling water and thoroughly mixed to ensure uniform colour blending. At that point, the clean, deflossed, and double-discarded cocoon is dipped in this solution. It is repeatedly mixed until the colour retention of the dipped cocoons is uniform. Cocoons should be dipped up to 50°C; any higher temperature will affect its sericin content, giving these cocoons a distorted appearance. To avoid de-coloration, remove the coloured cocoons from the solution and allow them to dry in a single layer under shade. Figure 3 shows the dyed cocoons. These coloured cocoons are ready to be transformed into desired items [8].

Figure 3: Dyed cocoons

2.5 Cocoon crafting

The Indian economy places a lot of emphasis on craftsmanship. One of the intriguing applications of results that will extend human capacity for autonomous labour and revenue generation is the specialty of cocoon production. In post-cocoon regions, the value decision is based on low risk and high salary value added by products ranging from 10% to 25% of total returns. The leftover silk cocoons are used to make a variety of items, including laurels, flower vases, wreaths, pen stands, dolls, tapestries, divider plates, timepieces, flower bouquets, and greeting cards. A few research institutes in Japan have developed silk paper in a variety of tones for use in constructing blossoms and light stands. To design objects made of plastic, steel, imitation adornments and textures, and metal, silk calfskin and a paint containing silk powder are employed. hand-woven products, hand-tied cocoons, and scarves and fabrics that have been hand-printed. Japan received deliveries of half-breed silk, net raw silk, silk town, and silk wave for use in creating undergarments, coats, sweaters, floor coverings, and other products. One of the unique characteristics of the handiworks is that they are made in different places and are therefore unique in terms of their craftsmanship, style, and colour. On exceptional occasions, officials and guests are presented with bouquets and garlands of rose flowers. Regular flowers only retain their freshness for a relatively brief period of time and ultimately dries. Additionally, it implies that the money used to purchase these distinctive but transient new blooms was wasted. Unexpectedly, if we give the guests cocoon-made flower wreaths or bundles as a token of our appreciation, they will take it home and keep it for a long time as a decorative accent. To support aesthetic allure and desire, Cocoon ensured that objects maintained their brilliance for a considerable amount of time. The use of cocoon-shaped goods is gaining ground and appeal as a craftsmanship movement [9].

The cocoon products were consistent size and shape. The soiled and stained cocoons were dismissed. The separated cocoons were going to be deflossed eventually. These deflossed cocoons were coloured and given legitimacy utilising cutting edges, scissors, etc. In accordance with the item setup. The chopped cocoon's crown portion was frequently employed in the creation of tiny beaded garlands, cards, and opulent items [9].

3. Results and Discussion

Petal-sized pieces of the coloured cocoons were cut out. By employing 3 to 4 cocoons, each cocoon was divided into 3 to 4 petals. It was shaped more compactly. By using glue petals were fixed. When the flower has dried, poke a pointy needle into the centre of it to attach a decorative wire, then bundle the lower portion of the flower which can serve as the flower's tail at the top. A green cocoon was chopped into the shape of leaves. Around the blossoms were arranged these leaves. In its place, a fake plastic leaf was frequently utilised. The flowers formed from cocoons are depicted in figure 4 [7].

Figure 4: cocoon flower

3.1 Cocoon flower bouquet

Cocoon flower bouquets come in two varieties: single flower bouquets and bundle bouquets. A single bouquet was created by attaching two or three flowers and a leaf to a branch-shaped green plastic wire. It was wrapped in a funnel-shaped clear transparent sheet with cello tape and lined with a coating paper. It would appear as if it were a brand-new rose bouquet. A bundle bouquet was created by combining 25 to 50 packs of various shades and colours

of cocoon flowers. The number of flower cocoons required is determined by the size and arrangement of the bouquet to be created as shown in the figure 5 [7].

Figure 5: Cocoon flower bouquet

3.2 Cocoon garland

The cocoons were cut with a scissor into floral and leaf shapes. Colored cocoons were used instead. Some gold-colored beads were added at the end of the cocoon flowers, trailed by a flower and beads again on the opposite hand with the help of a needle/string framing a state of garland. The number of cocoons needed to fill the wreath depends on its length. This is a rich-looking garland that can be planned in three lines with a central cocoon pendulum design. The garland with a weighty bouncy look required approximately 500 cocoons. Cocoon flower garlands are more elegant and last much longer. About 1 kg cut/pierced cocoons were used to make approximately 6 large garlands. Beaded white and coloured caps may enhance its visual appeal. This type of garland was light in weight, delicate with a nice appearance, and easy to convey a gift. The cocoon garland is depicted in Figure 6 [7].

Figure 6: Cocoon garland

3.3 Interior decoration products

Home decor items like birds, Lord Ganesha images, wall hangings, little mulberry or other trees, famous buildings like the Taj Mahal and the Snowman, or other items of stylish, trendy value that may demonstrate the creative talent of workmanship, were made by cocoons. The cocoons were divided into extremely small pieces of various designs, and these pieces were assembled to form certain forms that were then adhered on special paper or velvet. After being given an inventive touch by finishing, expensive glass was printed, presented, and offered for sale. These items are quite attractive and draw both customers and dignitaries [10]. The things made in a cocoon are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Cocoon home decors

4. Conclusion

The silk industry updates the concept to make sericulture a financially viable proposition, enabling it to compete successfully against other cash crops. Through natively accessible handling processes, usable results can be improved, resulting in increased compensation and personal financial gain. Craftsmanship skills are used to create ornaments such as garlands, flower jars, wreaths, pen stands, dolls, goldsmiths, tapestries, clocks, flower bouquets, and greeting cards. The silk-based material is used to create blooms, table lights, and to highlight textures, plastics, and steel. The promotion of the idea of considerable value growth through appropriate training, cross-disciplinary projects, and global advertising should be the focus of R&D organisations and sericulture offices in order to achieve a successful outcome employing the handcrafting concept of silk cut cocoons. recognising the length of value growth. A crucial component of the silk business is the silk cocoon. The sericin found in silk cocoons, however, is typically discarded. Sericin has a variety of useful components, and manufacturers are becoming more and more interested in using it in skin care products.

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